

The Physico-chemical Characteristics of the Oxides of Nickel from the Magneto-chemical Standpoint.

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Recent literature abounds in references to investigations on the methods of preparation and properties of the various oxides of nickel which are important from the standpoint of theory and their application as catalysers in important technical processes.

Leehand and Lepierre (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1892, *iii*, 7, 600) were the earliest to report that the two oxides prepared by the ignition of anhydrous nickel sulphate were crystalline modifications of the parent salt and their densities were slightly different from each other. Later Le Blanc and Saeghe (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1926, **32**, 58) by heating the basic carbonate of nickel to various temperatures ranging from 550° to 1220° obtained nickelous oxide of colours varying from dark grey to greyish green. They, however, showed that most of the oxides possessed the normal cubic structure as evidenced by the patterns of the X-ray diffraction and from this they concluded that there was only one type of NiO formed. The black colour of the oxide was explained on the fact that the oxide adsorbed oxygen from the air forming an adsorption complex.

Prasad and Tendulkar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1403) studied the influence of temperature of preparation on the physical properties of nickelous oxide. They found that with rise in temperature of preparation, the density and the electrical resistance of NiO increased and the rate of dissolution in sulphuric acid and the catalytic activity in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide decreased. They concluded that there were two distinct forms of nickelous oxide, the black oxide prepared at 400° and the greenish yellow oxide obtained at 1000°. They ascribed these changes in properties to changes (i) in particle size, (ii) in crystalline form, and (iii) in intramolecular structure.

Recently, Cairns and Ott (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 527) from an X-ray study of nickelous oxide have shown that the two

modifications described are identical and have the usual face-centered type of lattice and are not different from each other in an intramolecular way.

On the other hand, a number of higher oxides of nickel have been reported. Rose (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1851, **84**, 571), Glaser (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, **36**, 1), Baubigny (*Compt. rend.*, 1878, **87**, 1082; 1905, **141**, 1232), Wohler and Blaz (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1921, **27**, 406), Vaubel (*Chem. Z.*, 1922, **46**, 978) and Lunde (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **162**, 352) have reported the preparation of oxides such as Ni_3O_4 , Ni_2O_3 and NiO_2 .

More recently, Goralevich (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **62**, 1165) has reported the existence of a number of higher oxides of nickel, e. g., Ni_2O_3 , Ni_3O_4 and NiO_2 . Besides these, he has also found evidence for the existence of the following composite and less stable oxides:— Ni_5O_9 , Ni_6O_{11} , Ni_3O_5 , Ni_6O_{17} , Ni_7O_{12} , Ni_8O_{15} , Ni_5O_8 , $\text{Ni}_{11}\text{O}_{17}$, Ni_9O_{16} , Ni_8O_{13} , Ni_5O_7 , Ni_2O_3 .

The later work of Hendricks, Jefferson and Schultz (*Z. Kryst.*, 1930, **73**, 376) has thrown doubt on the accuracy of Goralevich's work.

In view of the above conflicting evidence as to the nature of the black nickelous oxide and the the existence or otherwise of the higher oxides of nickel, it was considered desirable to investigate this problem from the magneto-chemical standpoint.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In general the experiments carried out in this investigation were the following:—

1. Preparation of the nickel oxides by various methods.
2. Estimation of nickel, and the determination of the chemical composition of the oxides.
3. Experimental determination of the magnetic susceptibility χ of the various samples.
4. Experimental determination of the temperature coefficient of χ for the two samples of NiO .
5. Adsorption of oxygen by the two oxides.

The following methods were employed to prepare the oxides under investigation:—

(a) By heating nickel nitrate (extra pure) very strongly on the blow-pipe flame.

(b) By melting nickel chloride with potassium chlorate.

(c) By treating nickel salts in solution with potassium hypochlorite aq.

(d) By heating the hydroxide (i) on the blow-pipe flame, and (ii) on the Bunsen burner flame.

(e) By heating nickel carbonate in air.

(f) Treating the nickel chloride solution with hydrogen peroxide in cold and afterwards adding the alcoholic potash solution.

The amount of nickel in these oxides was estimated by the dimethylglyoxime gravimetric method.

Some of the results were checked by the potassium cyanide volumetric method and as this involved the use of potassium cyanide for most of the work, the gravimetric method alone was employed.

From the analytical investigations of the reaction products obtained in the various methods the following results were obtained.

TABLE I

Method of preparation.	Wt. of the product.	Oxide expected to be formed.	Wt. of nickel	
			Obs.	Calc.
1. Heating the nitrate on the blow-pipe flame	0.0699 g. (dark green)	NiO	0.0547 g.	0.0551 g.
2. Heating the carbonate on the blow-pipe flame	0.0706 (black)	NiO	0.0591	0.0556
3. Heating the mixture of nickel nitrate and potassium chlorate on the blow-pipe flame, till fusion	0.0773 (black)	Ni ₂ O ₃	0.0547	0.0549
4. Heating the hydroxide on the blow-pipe flame	0.0790	NiO	0.0614	0.0622
5. By adding sodium hypochlorite to nickel nitrate solution	0.0734 Some hydrate formation took place and the weight of Ni was found to be less than that of oxygen	Ni ₂ O ₃	0.0941	0.0521
6. Treating the nickel chloride solution with hydrogen peroxide in cold and afterwards adding the alcoholic potash solution	0.0469 A green mass was first obtained which turned black on drying	NiO ₂	0.0351	0.0369

As pure NiO was expected to be formed from methods, 2 and 4, the reaction products resulting from these methods were analysed for Ni only. The weight of oxygen was determined by difference.

In the case of methods No. 1 and No. 3, observed amounts of nickel compared well with the calculated amounts. From this coincidence it may appear as if the reaction products were pure oxides. But these results are not convincing, unless the above conclusions are confirmed by the determination of the oxygen content and physical properties of these substances, such as densities and magnetic susceptibilities.

Density determinations of all the oxides were carried out by suspending them in toluene and employing the usual specific gravity bottle method.

A Gouy's type balance was used for the magnetic measurements. It consisted of a very sensitive Sartorius balance placed on a hollow wooden box. One of the two pans of the balance was replaced by a half pan similar to the type used in Sp. G. determinations of lighter bodies. To this half pan was soldered a hollow copper cylinder about three inches in length and two inches in diameter through which a copper rod R having a hook at the end was passed and this rod could be moved upwards and downwards inside the hollow cylinder by means of a screw, which provided the arrangement for raising or lowering the sample tube inside the magnetic field. The balance resembled the equipment shown in Baird and Tatlock's catalogue.

Determination of χ .—After setting the balance in order, its standardisation was undertaken. Copper sulphate (A. R.) of known susceptibility was put in the sample tube up to a definite mark and the pull exerted on the sample tube in the magnetic field was measured. By using the relation $mg = \frac{1}{2}AH^2(K_1 - K_2)$ the value, of AH^2 was determined (K_1 and K_2 in this equation represent the volume susceptibilities of the material of the cylinder and the medium). A current of 1.5 amps. was passed through the solenoids and the value of AH^2 was found to be 0.7162.

In order to test the accuracy of this value of AH^2 the susceptibilities of the following known substances were measured and were found to compare well with the well known values of χ for these substances.

TABLE II

Name of the substance.	Observed value of $\chi \times 10^6$.	Actual value of $\chi \times 10^6$.
Cobalt sulphate (crystals) extra pure	36.95	37.0
Nickel sulphate, extra pure	15.80	16.0
Iron ammonium sulphate, extra pure	31.50	32.0

Magnetic susceptibility and density determination by the above methods gave the following results.

TABLE III:

Oxide obtained by.	Wt. of the product.	Wt. of the pull.	Vol. susceptibility + $\chi \times 10^6$.	Mass susceptibility + $\chi \times 10^6$.	Density.
1. Heating the nitrate very strongly on the blow-pipe flame	0.9613 g.	0.0186 g.	271.763	53.4	5.2
2. Heating the carbonate on the blow-pipe flame	0.6756	0.0020	45.504	8.12	5.6
3. Heating the mixture of nickel nitrate and potassium chlorate to fusion	0.9608	0.0038	56.467	10.88	4.8
4. Heating the hydroxide on the blow-pipe flame	0.9034	0.0033	47.869	9.97	5.19
5. Adding sodium hypochlorite to nickel nitrate soln.	0.4196	0.0036	52.627	23.49	2.24
6. Treating the nickel chloride solution with hydrogen peroxide in cold and afterwards adding alcoholic potash solution	0.9126	0.0035	46.856	9.52	4.8

In all the above pull measurements the tube was filled to the same volume and the current passed in all the cases was also the same.

The value of χ for the oxide prepared by the first method was found to be 53.4×10^{-6} . This compared very favourably with the value 53.7×10^{-6} obtained by Honda (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1914, 3, 113; 1915, 4, 215) for pure nickel oxide.

It will be shown later that this value of χ was not a proof of the composition of NiO and that the coincidence with the value obtained by Honda was purely accidental as the correct value of χ for NiO has been found to be 9.56×10^{-6} . The high value (53.4×10^{-6}) is due to the partial reduction of the oxide to the metallic nickel owing to the introduction of a small quantity of carbon from the blow-pipe flame.

In the first stage of ignition a black sample (the value of χ being 9.12×10^{-6}) was obtained which on further heating for 6 to 8 hours gave value of χ even higher than 53.4×10^{-6} and it was noticed that the tube began to stick to the poles of the electromagnet. The appearance of ferromagnetism introduced a new complication and the investigation was then pursued as follows:

The ferromagnetic variety obtained above when heated in an electric furnace to a temperature of 1000° lost its property of ferromagnetism, the value of χ was found to be 53.4×10^{-6} , which is identical with our first value. On further heating the sample it was found that the value of susceptibility showed a further decrease. A plausible explanation of this might be that a compound of the type Ni_3O_4 has been formed at some particular temperature. As Ni_3O_4 is analogous to Fe_3O_4 (a highly magnetic substance) and as Fe_3O_4 decomposes to FeO , similarly the compound Ni_3O_4 (ferromagnetic) should undergo decomposition to NiO (paramagnetic). If it is so then the above views regarding the magnetic properties of the compound, on heating, could be qualitatively accounted for. In order to provisionally fix the temperature of production of the ferromagnetic sample, a series of experiments were made which gave the following results.

TABLE IV.

Process.	Colour.	$\chi \times 10^6$.
1. Heating the black oxide on the blow-pipe flame	Dark green	Ferromagnetic
2. Heating the black variety in the electric furnace	Dark to green	Black 9.11 Green 9.56
3. Heating the black oxide in a sealed crucible	Dark green after 6 to 8 hours	Ferromagnetic
4. Heating the black oxide in a silica tube	The colour becomes green on continuous heating	9.56 to 10.01
5. Heating the ferromagnetic variety in an electric furnace	Colour changes from dark green to distinct green	The value of χ falls to 9.56

From Table IV it is quite obvious that the samples obtained on blow-pipe flame yield very high values of χ , while the products electrically obtained are feebly paramagnetic. This difference in the magnetic nature of the products could be accounted for in various ways such as the following:

(1). Formation of Ni_3O_4 and its subsequent change to NiO . This view had to be discarded altogether because of the non-formation of the ferromagnetic sample in the electric furnace at any temperature whatsoever. And the values of χ never exceeded the figure 9.56×10^{-6} in any case. If at a particular temperature, Ni_3O_4 had been formed, the results would have been identical both when the sample was heated either electrically or on a Bunsen flame.

(2). The magnetic field of the electric furnace might be responsible for the production of a different type of NiO . But this again would not explain the magnetic behaviour of the products obtained in the silica tubes which were similar to the products of the electric furnace. It could thus be safely inferred that the presence or absence of the magnetic field was without any effect on the magnetic nature of the products obtained in the two cases.

(3). While the products of reaction or decomposition were being heated on the blow-pipe flame, it is possible that a small amount of carbon or unburnt gas might have found entrance into the reaction mixture and this might have resulted in the formation of traces of free metallic nickel, by the reduction of the oxide, which being highly ferromagnetic might have rendered the sample ferromagnetic on the whole. This possibility is altogether ruled out when the product is obtained in an electric furnace.

(4). The gaseous products evolved during the decomposition might have changed the nature of the product formed.

The following experiments were, therefore, carried out to settle these points.

I. A small amount of carbon was added to the black oxide and the mixture again heated in the electric furnace more strongly. This resulted in the production of a very strongly ferromagnetic sample.

II. (a) The black oxide was heated in sealed crucibles on the blow-pipe flame. The resulting products were ferromagnetic in character.

(b) When silica tubes were used instead of the crucibles, the samples produced gave values of χ identical with those obtained in the electric furnace. This proves the entrance of carbon and gases through porous crucibles as opposed to the silica tubes.

III. When a ferromagnetic variety was brought in contact with a magnet it was found that a very small part of the sample was

attracted to the magnet and this on analysis was found to be metallic nickel.

IV. In order to study the influence of temperature on the nature of the resulting products, the ferromagnetic variety was heated in an oxy-acetylene and oxy-coal gas flame, respectively. In both cases the value of χ fell very low. Paramagnetic black oxide when heated under similar conditions and cooled showed no change in the values of χ .

The results of these experiments, when taken together, lead definitely to the view that the ferromagnetic sample is the result of the reduction of nickel oxide to nickel. This view finds support from the following work on the temperature coefficient of χ of the ferromagnetic variety.

Temperature Coefficient.

In order to determine the variation of χ with T a very small electric furnace was devised as follows:—

Two rectangular mica plates were taken, round which a very fine 'eureka' wire was wound in opposite directions so that the current flowing in one may cancel the magnetic effect of the current flowing in the other. The number of turns on both the plates was also identical. These wires were covered from outside by two similar mica plates held together with small supports of fine copper wire. The temperature could thus be very easily regulated by adjusting the strength of the current flowing through the circuit.

This small furnace with two sets of mica plates, the distance of which could be changed, was introduced in the gap, each plate being a little apart from the pole piece. The sample tube was introduced in the usual manner in the gap and so inside the two mica plates. The weight of the sample tube along with the oxide was determined every time (at every temperature) before putting the field on. Afterwards the tube was weighed in the field, the difference between the two weighings gave us the pull. In this way the effect of the current flowing in the furnace, if any, could be eliminated. Now as the mica plates got heated they also raised the temperature of the adjoining poles which changed the value of AH^2 . To avoid this, an attempt was made to keep the two magnets at almost the same temperature throughout the experiment by a special cooling arrangement.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF OXIDES OF Ni 611

Cooling arrangement.—The magnets were covered by two double walled vessels of almost the same shape as the pole pieces in which cold water was circulated. This kept the magnets at a uniform temperature though the temperature of the gap was very near to 400°.

While studying the variations of χ with T in the case of ferromagnetic variety the following results were obtained.

TABLE V.

$AH^2=1.9272$. Wt. of the sample = 0.2567 g.

Current passed in the furnace.	Temp.	Pull.	$\chi \times 10^6$.
0.0 amp.	29.4°	0.0082 g.	32.48
0.1	73.8	0.0081	32.07
0.2	129.0	0.00805	31.87
0.28	146.5	0.0080	31.66
0.35	231.8	0.0079	31.26
0.38	292.8	0.0078	30.85
0.40	355.4	0.0077	30.44
0.41	362.0	0.0077	30.44
0.42	366.0	0.0032	12.63

From Table V it is evident that at 365° the ferromagnetic variety loses its ferromagnetism altogether and becomes moderately paramagnetic yielding the valuable information that metallic nickel is the cause of the ferromagnetism of the so-called nickel oxide as the temperature 365° coincides with the 'Curie point' of nickel.

A study of the temperature variation of χ of green and black variety of the oxides was undertaken and the results obtained are given in the following table.

TABLE VI.

$AH^2=1.9272$. Wt. of the green oxide= 0.2041 g. Wt. of the black oxide = 0.1284 g.

Current passed in the furnace.	Green oxide			Black oxide		
	Temp.	Pull.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	Temp.	Pull.	$\chi \times 10^6$.
0.00 amp.	28.6°	0.0019 g.	9.48	25.0°	0.00115 g.	9.11
0.15	66.2	0.00185	9.22	57.2	0.0011	8.71
0.25	114.6	0.00175	8.72	129.6	0.0010	7.93
0.28	141.4	0.0017	8.45	204.2	0.0009	7.13
0.30	191.2	0.0016	7.94	242.8	0.00085	6.72
0.35	248.6	0.0015	7.43	319.2	0.00075	5.94
0.38	292.6	0.0014	6.90	351.4	0.0007	5.60
0.40	351.6	0.0013	6.318			

Although the original values of χ for the two samples are different the curves for χ and T in both the cases run parallel and the changes in values of χ per unit temperature within this range are identical. These results will be discussed later.

Adsorption of Oxygen by the Two Nickelous Oxides.

Investigations on this point were necessary as the black oxide of nickel on desorption of oxygen becomes green. The reverse phenomenon does not appear to have been investigated at all.

The apparatus used for the purpose was Lunge's gas volumeter, and it was modified to suit our purpose as follows:

A glass tube of about 1" in diameter at the top drawn at the bottom to a fine bore of about 1/10" in diameter, and about 2 ft. in length was connected by means of a special mercury-rubber tubing to a 50 c.c. burette having a three-way cock at the top. By means of this three-way cock, the burette could be connected with the sample tube or with the calcium chloride cylinders which were introduced for drying the gas passing through them.

In the first instance the burette was filled with air by means of a pulley arrangement which helped in raising or lowering the mercury in the burette.

Fresh and dry air was introduced by the said device and the connection with the sample tube was made and both the time and level of the mercury in the burette was noted.

After 24 hours the oxygen was collected in an aspirator from which it was introduced in the burette. The observations in the case of black oxide yielded negative results while the green variety clearly manifested an adsorption, though small. The values of χ were found to be :

$$\chi \times 10^6 \text{ before adsorption} = 9.38$$

$$\chi \times 10^6 \text{ of green sample after a slight adsorption of } O_2 = 9.26$$

$$\chi \times 10^6 \text{ of black sample} = 9.11$$

This clearly indicates that the value of χ tends to change towards the direction of the black variety when oxygen is adsorbed by the green sample. The next two sets of experiments were performed to get further information on this point.

(a) Freshly prepared oxygen was passed over the green oxide which had already absorbed oxygen both at room temperature and at 260° for over 8 hours. It was found that no further change in the value of χ occurred at all beyond that recorded above.

(b) To investigate the matter still further a little of the oxide was placed on a perforated plate sufficiently above the mixture of potassium chlorate and manganese dioxide so that the freshly evolved oxygen may get a chance to come in contact with a large surface of the green oxide.

Even in this case no change was observed and the green oxide retained its green colour and did not assume the black colour. While the black oxide easily becomes green on losing adsorbed oxygen when heated, the reverse experiment seems to be possible only when the green oxide comes into contact with active oxygen and evidently the value of 9.11×10^{-6} for χ is indicative of the limit of the adsorbability of active oxygen by this oxide.

The Case of the Oxide of the Composition Ni_2O_3 .

During the preparation of nickel oxides by various methods, a sample, black in colour, which on analysis found to be Ni_2O_3 , was obtained (*cf.* Table I, No. 5). Its density and susceptibility were also determined the values being 4.8 and 10.88×10^{-6} respectively.

As in the case of NiO previously described, important differences in magnetic properties were noticed when the sample was prepared in the electric furnace. It was, therefore, considered desirable to check these results in an analogous manner.

By changing the method of preparation of the oxide (by using electric furnace instead of Bunsen burner or blow-pipe flame for heating), the final product obtained was similar in all chemical and physical characteristics to NiO. The values for density and χ were 6.6 and 9.58×10^{-6} respectively. The analytical results for oxygen and nickel also denoted a composition NiO.

The experiment was repeated several times and the results indicated that Ni_2O_3 could not be formed by method No. 3 (Table I).

From this it is concluded that the production of Ni_2O_3 by No. 3 method on the blow-pipe flame must have been accidental owing to the introduction of certain impurities from the flame.

The presence of nickel in these cases was also established by the 'Curie point' method, as well as from actual analysis of oxygen and nickel ratio.

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.

1. Various methods used in the preparation of nickel oxides result in reaction products, many of which on analysis are found to be chemically identical, though they possess distinct colours.

2. Two prominent colours, black and green, are generally exhibited by different oxide samples. In certain cases compounds of intermediate type composed of varying quantities of the two oxides, possessing colour dark green to faint black, are also obtained.

3. While the difference in colour is attributed to the difference in various physical conditions of the samples, *viz.*, (a) particle size, (b) crystalline form, (c) intramolecular nature (Prasad and Tendulkar, *loc. cit.*), it has been shown that traces of adsorbed gases, particularly of oxygen, and the presence of other impurities in minute quantities can bring about a marked change in the colour and magnetic properties of the reaction products.

4. That the presence of traces of impurity which gets introduced in the sample while it is being heated, cooled and purified, or while

it is being carried to some other similar operation, can change both the physical and chemical nature of the substance to a very great extent, is fully borne out by the fact that the sample obtained on the blow-pipe flame contains free nickel and carbon and gives highly ferromagnetic product due to the presence of free nickel.

5. That in these oxides, the presence of free nickel is analytically difficult to estimate, is due to the fact that the presence of carbon renders the estimations inaccurate, the amount of nickel found by estimations being always lower than the actual amount. The value of χ (53.4×10^{-6}) for nickel oxide points to the fact that Honda's compound was made on the blow-pipe flame and contained traces of free nickel as impurity.

The preparation of nickelous oxide in an electric furnace gives a substance which on analysis is found to be chemically pure NiO and the value of χ for this never exceeds 9.56×10^{-6} .

6. That the higher value of χ reported before is due to the presence of varying qualities of nickel. This view has been confirmed by many other experiments, the most important of them being the determination of the susceptibility of the ferromagnetic variety at various temperatures. The sudden change in the value of χ at 365° , which is the same as the 'Curie point' of the metallic nickel, clearly shows that the ferromagnetic variety does contain traces of free nickel which becomes paramagnetic at the 'Curie point'.

The formation of ferromagnetic variety by heating a mixture of carbon and nickel oxide in the furnace, sticking of a part of the ferromagnetic oxide to a magnet which on subsequent analysis is found to be nickel, as well as the results obtained from the silica tube experiments, support the same view.

7. That the value of χ for nickelous oxide prepared in the silica tube in place of a crucible is also 9.56×10^{-6} adds further support to the above view.

8. The χ and T curves of the two nickelous oxides run parallel showing thereby that both the varieties have got almost the same temperature coefficient for χ . The black oxide retains the lower value of χ throughout the experiments and clearly establishes that while the two nickel oxides are chemically identical the lower value of χ for the black sample is due to some difference in its physical nature such as adsorption of oxygen.

9. The results of adsorption experiments are in accordance with X-ray diffraction photographs obtained by Cairns and Ott (*loc. cit.*).

These two investigators attribute the black colour of the oxide as being due to the adsorption of active oxygen. It has been found that the black oxide on heating very strongly is turned green owing to the liberation of adsorbed oxygen. Adsorption results indicate that the green variety can adsorb more oxygen than the black one which already contains some oxygen. The adsorption of oxygen by the green variety tends to lower its value of susceptibility as shown by the adsorption experiments. If sufficient adsorption of oxygen takes place by the green variety, it is possible that it may become black giving the same value of χ as the black sample.

10. The various oxides reported in literature were most probably formed by the introduction of certain impurities from outside. The only oxide of nickel which can be produced under various experimental conditions is NiO, the existence of which has been proved definitely. This possesses definite physical and chemical characteristics.

11. From the adsorption results obtained in this investigation and which are in line with the X-ray work of Cairns and Ott (*loc. cit.*), the view that the intramolecular changes may be brought about seems to be superfluous as all the facts can be accounted for on the impurities, oxygen and nickel getting incorporated with the NiO during experimentation.

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